

Research

Impact of Spatio-Temporal Land Cover Changes on Land Surface Temperature over Dormaa from 1990-2020

Abraham Okrah^{1,2,3,*}, Nana Agyemang Prempeh³, Caleb Mensah^{3,4}, Robert Johnson⁵, Naomi Kumi³, Frederick Otu-Larbi³ and Richard Kyere-Boateng³

¹Collaborative Innovation Center on Forecast and Evaluation of Meteorological Disaster, Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology, Nanjing 210044, China

²Jiangsu Key Laboratory of Agricultural Meteorology, College of Applied Meteorology, Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology, Nanjing 210044, China

³Department of Atmospheric and Climate Sciences, School of Geosciences, University of Energy and Natural Resources, P. O. Box 214, Sunyani, Ghana

⁴Faculty of Agric Sciences, Mendel University, Brno CZ-603 00, Czech Republic

⁵Department of Meteorology and Climate Science, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology

Abstract: Land surface temperature (LST) and surface air temperature (SAT) are important environmental variables that describe the temperature of the Earth's surface as measured by satellite sensors or ground-based instruments. Changes in land cover, such as deforestation, urbanization, and agriculture, can have a significant impact on LST, as they alter the surface energy balance and affect the amount of solar radiation that is absorbed or reflected by the land surface. The effects of increased LST are often complex and depend on a range of factors, including the specific location, the type and intensity of urbanization, and the surrounding natural environment. However, it is clear that high LSTs and SAT can have a range of negative impacts on both natural and built environments, and that efforts to reduce LSTs can have significant benefits for human health, the environment, and the economy. This study examines the impact of spatio-temporal land cover changes (built-ups) on land surface temperature (LST) over Dormaa from 1990-2020. Using the Mann-Kendall trend test, remote sensing data, and GIS techniques, we analyse the relationship between land cover changes and LST at the local scale, taking into account factors such as vegetation cover, land use patterns, and weather conditions. The analysis of LULCC, LST, and SAT with their corresponding percentage annual rate of change showed a deterministic factor $R=0.89$, with a significant F-change of 0.014 at a 95% confidence interval of their difference. The results provide strong evidence that the increase in LST and SAT across the years over the Dormaa area correlated with the significant changes in land cover as observed from 1990 – 2020. The most significant land cover changes were observed within the Dormaa Municipal, which also recorded the highest LST and SAT anomaly change of 0.091°C compared to the other districts. The results further showed that the rapid urbanization that occurred between 2000-2020 in the Dormaa Municipal was the primary cause of the observed increase in LST and SAT. The quick changes in the land cover, which caused a greater portion of the green vegetated surface in the Dormaa Municipal to be converted to a more non-transpiring and reduced evaporative built-up environment for housing, provision of social amenities, and supporting other significant socio-economic activities, resulted in an increased LST and SAT. Our results indicate that land cover changes have had a significant impact on LST over Dormaa

during the study period. In particular, urbanization and agricultural land use changes have led to increases in LST, while changes in forest cover have had a more complex relationship with temperature, depending on factors such as the type and intensity of forest management. We also found that the relationship between land cover changes and LST is non-linear and dependent on interactions between multiple factors, highlighting the importance of considering the specific context when analysing this relationship. Our study provides new insights into the complex relationship between land cover changes and LST at the local scale, which can be used to inform local decision-making, such as land use planning and management, and contribute to our broader understanding of the impact of human activities on the environment. The study also urges all interested parties to ensure and integrate vegetation conservation in modern city planning models, as green environments act as carbon sinks (a role in global warming) by implementing rules and regulations in the districts, particularly in the Dormaa Municipal.

Keywords: Surface Air Temperature; Land Use Land Cover Change; Land Surface Temperature, ArcGIS

*Corresponding Author okrahbraham2014@gmail.com

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1. Introduction

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's (IPCC) Fifth (1) and Sixth (2) Assessment Reports affirm that global climate has undergone significant changes (3) over the past century. The 2013-2014 Fifth Assessment Report established that the Earth's surface temperature had risen by 0.85°C (1.5°F) between 1880 and 2012 primarily due to human activities (4) such as the burning of fossil fuels and deforestation. Recent decades saw the rate of warming accelerate (5), with the period between 1983 and 2012 being the warmest 30-year period in the last 1400 years (6). The Sixth Assessment Report, published in August 2021, updates and expands upon these findings, stating that the Earth's surface temperature has risen by 1.1°C (2°F) since the late 19th century, unequivocally attributed to human activities (2). Additionally, the report highlights the rate of warming acceleration, with the last decade being the warmest on record. To limit global warming to 1.5°C (2.7°F) above pre-industrial levels, the report stresses the necessity for immediate and unprecedented changes in all aspects of society, including energy, land use (4,7,8), transportation, and industry (3). Overall, the reports underscore the pressing need for prompt action to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (2,4,9,10) and limit the impacts of climate change. They also emphasize that the longer we wait to take action, the more difficult and costly it will be to address the challenges posed by climate change.

Studies (6,11) have confirmed and expanded upon the findings of the IPCC's Fifth and Sixth Assessment Reports, providing further evidence of the significant and ongoing impacts of climate change. A study (10) found that extreme heatwaves have become more frequent and more severe due to climate change, with the likelihood of such events increasing by a factor of 20 in some regions (12). Another study (10) showed that the Greenland Ice Sheet is melting at an unprecedented rate, with the rate of ice loss increasing by a factor of four over the past two decades (12). These and other recent studies provide clear and compelling evidence that climate change is real, happening now, and having significant impacts on our planet and its inhabitants (2-4,6,8). They also underscore the urgent need for immediate and

sustained action to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, mitigate the impacts of climate change, and build resilience to its inevitable effects.

Further studies indicate that the global temperature has exhibited a positive trend in the spatiotemporal pattern (6,11,13), although some variability still exists on regional and local scales with respect to extreme temperature events (14). These fluctuations and changes in temperature have a significant impact on the well-being and livelihoods of organisms (7,15–17). Climate variability and change pose a serious threat to many countries, particularly the vulnerable and poorest developing nations (2) like Ghana. The West African region (1–3), including Ghana, is projected to witness an increasing trend in temperature according to the IPCC reports. Extreme weather conditions, such as record-breaking rainfall events, have been witnessed globally in the previous decade. A study conducted on the Central and Greater Accra regions of Ghana (11) has reported a 1.0 °C increase in annual maximum temperature between 1981-2009. The study suggests that if appropriate mitigation measures are not taken, the Central and Greater Accra regions, along with other areas in the transition belt where Dormaa (18) is located in Ghana, would continue to experience adverse weather events and a rise in temperature.

Recent studies have also shown a similar trend of increasing temperature in the West African region (6,8,19), including Ghana. For instance, a study (11) found that the annual mean temperature in Ghana had increased by about 1.0°C from 1960 to 2016. The study (19) indicated that the temperature in West Africa, including Ghana, is projected to increase by about 1.5-3.0°C by mid-century, depending on the level of greenhouse gas emissions. These findings are consistent with the previous IPCC reports (1,2) and suggest that urgent action is needed to mitigate the impacts of climate change in Ghana and the West African region as a whole. Additionally, recent studies have also highlighted the potential impacts of climate change on various sectors, including agriculture, water resources, and health, in Ghana (6,8,11). These studies underscore the need for integrated and adaptive strategies to build resilience and reduce vulnerability to the impacts of climate change in Ghana.

Land cover change (LULC) is a well-studied factor that contributes significantly to environmental change on local and regional scales (8,20–23). Urbanization-induced changes (8) can have negative impacts on the earth-atmosphere system, including biodiversity loss, desertification, and climate change, leading to warming. In a study on sustainable human well-being in Namibia, (7) found that agricultural activities and land abandonment due to degradation were responsible for forest-land loss and fragmentation, posing a threat to ecological biodiversity (20) and contributing to climate change. Another study (8) investigated the impact of land cover change on the land surface temperature of Kumasi in Ghana, West Africa, and found that the rapid urban expansion and development in the city resulted in the loss of natural green surfaces, which were replaced by non-transpiring built-up surfaces. Similar studies (21,22,24) have also shown an increase in land surface temperature (LST) as a result of urbanization. While urbanization provides opportunities for economic growth, it can also ensure access to basic needs such as education, healthcare, water, transportation, and electricity for individuals.

The urbanization process in Ghana, as in many other parts of the world, has been found to affect Land Surface Temperature (LST) (2,6,8,11,20). The urban heat island effect (8), which involves the absorption and re-emission of heat by urban infrastructure such as buildings and roads, is one of the factors that contribute to higher LSTs in urban areas compared to rural areas. Several studies have investigated the relationship between urbanization and LST in Ghana. For example, a study by (11) focused on Accra, the capital city of Ghana, and found that LSTs were significantly higher in urban areas than in rural areas. Additionally, the study showed that LSTs were highest in areas with intermediate levels of urbanization. Another study (8) focused on Kumasi, the second-largest city in Ghana, and found that densely built-up areas with a high percentage of impervious surfaces such as roads and buildings had the highest LSTs. These findings are

consistent with the broader literature on the impact of urbanization on LST, which indicates that the relationship between urbanization and LST is non-linear and depends on factors such as the intensity and type of urbanization, weather conditions, and vegetation cover.

The Dormaa area has undergone significant changes (18,25,26) in land use due to population growth since the 1960s. The rapid growth of the Dormaa Municipal district, coupled with unplanned infrastructural expansion in the savanna and transition belts (11), has contributed to the formation of microclimates and urban heat islands (8), which have been linked to global climate change. The focus of this research is to examine the relationship between spatiotemporal land cover changes and land surface temperature at the local scale in Dormaa. This study can provide context-specific information to inform local decision-making on land use planning and management by taking into account unique factors such as local land use patterns (7,22,23), vegetation cover, and weather conditions. Moreover, this study can contribute to the broader body of knowledge on the impact of human activities on land surface temperature by providing new insights and data from a previously understudied location, which can further refine our understanding of the complex relationships between land cover changes, human activities, and climate.

This study uses LULC data from LANDSAT and surface air temperature (SAT) data from ERA-5 to measure the impact of LULC on Land Surface Temperature (LST) in the Dormaa Municipal (DM), Dormaa East (DE), and Dormaa West (DW) Districts. The study has three main objectives: (i) to detect changes in mean and extreme temperature variables across the districts, (ii) to identify the most temperature-sensitive district in the Dormaa area, and (iii) to evaluate the effects of LULC change on LST and SAT trends, while proposing mitigation strategies for the Dormaa area. Understanding the relationship between land cover changes and LST in Dormaa is crucial for developing effective strategies to mitigate the negative impacts of urbanization, agricultural expansion, and deforestation on local climate patterns and temperatures.

2.0 Materials and Methodology

2.1 Study Area Description

The Dormaa Municipality is an administrative district located in the western part of the Bono Region of Ghana (Figure 1). The population growth and development in basic infrastructure led to the district's elevation to a municipality and the subsequent creation of two other districts, the Dormaa East and West districts (18,25,26). The municipality's geographical coordinates lie within longitudes 3° West and 3° 30' West and latitudes 7° North and 7° 30' North, with a total land area of 1,210.28 km², which constitutes about 3.1% of the combined land area of the Bono and Ahafo Regions.

Figure 1: The study area is located in Ghana and is indicated by regions a, b, and c on the map. These regions correspond to the DE, DM, and DW districts respectively.

The area's topography is generally undulating, with elevations ranging from 180 m to 375 m above sea level. The region falls within the wet semi-equatorial climate zone with a double-maximum rainfall regime (11). The mean annual rainfall in Dormaa is approximately 1,200mm, and the highest mean temperature is about 30°C, occurring between March and April, while the lowest is about 26.1°C in August (11). The major vegetation types in the area are the Semi-Equatorial Forest, semi-deciduous forest, and high grassland. The climatic conditions of the districts are favourable for the cultivation of various cash crops such as cocoa, coffee, and food crops such as plantain, cocoyam, and cassava. The area is well-drained, as evidenced by the network of rivers spread throughout the district, which are primarily used as a source of water for the cultivation of vegetables such as tomatoes, pepper, and okra during the dry season. About six out of ten households (68.4%) in the districts are engaged in agriculture, with crop farming being the primary occupation of most households in the municipality (65.4%) (18).

2.1.1 Land Use/Land Cover Change data

This study utilized remote sensing techniques (8,19,20,27) for acquiring and processing LULC change data. One of the major limitations of remote sensing is its inability to obtain data and information through cloud cover, which can lead to confusion between distinct phenomena that appear similar to the sensor (8). However, remote sensing has been effectively used for monitoring and identifying changes in both aquatic (14,22,24) and terrestrial environments (19,28). For instance, (8) employed remote sensing techniques to assess the impact of LULCC on surface temperature in Kumasi, Ghana. Additionally, remotely sensed data has been utilized by LULC change researchers to provide information on resource inventory and land use, as well as to identify, monitor, and quantify changing patterns in landscapes (7,20,29).

The Landsat imageries used in this study were downloaded from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) via the Earth Explorer website. Landsat 4-5, 7, 2, and 8 satellite imageries for 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2020 (Table 1) were downloaded and utilized for land cover extraction. These same Landsat imageries were also utilized in extracting the Land Surface Temperature (LST) for DE, DW, and DM for the aforementioned years.

Satellite sensor	WRS path/row	Date of acquisition	Spatial resolution	Spectral resolution	Source
Landsat 4–5 TM	120/039	1990-08-28	30 m	7 bands	Earthexplorer.org
Landsat 7 ETM+	195/055	2000-01-01	30 m	8 bands	Earthexplorer.org
Landsat 7 ETM+	195/055	2010-01-28	30 m	8 bands	Earthexplorer.org
Landsat 8 OLI	195/055	2020-02-20	30 m	11 bands	Earthexplorer.org

Table 1: Summary of Landsat Data used.

2.1.2 Surface Air Temperature (SAT) data

Spatiotemporal data for scientific research in the Dormaa subregion is limited, as noted in previous studies (18). To overcome this limitation, researchers often rely on reanalysis and satellite datasets. In this study, the surface temperature data used was obtained from the fifth generation of the European Re-Analysis (ERA-5), which offers improved horizontal resolution (9 km) and temporal resolution (hourly) compared to previous products like ERA-Interim.

To extract temperature data for the study sites the latitude and longitude of each site were used to retrieve geo-specific data points from ERA5-Land. The mean temperature from 1990 to 2020 was analysed, and the hourly data was integrated into daily and monthly aggregates (30) for further analysis.

To visualize the spatio-temporal temperature distribution, time series plots were generated to show the daily and monthly progression of temperature values within the selected study sites. The temperature data obtained from ERA-5 was originally recorded in Kelvin, but it was converted to Celsius for the purposes of this study. This conversion was carried out using appropriate conversion formulas. Overall, the use of satellite data and reanalysis products allowed for the analysis of temperature trends and anomalies over a large spatial and temporal scale, providing valuable insights into the study area.

2.2 Land Cover Analysis

ArcGIS 10.8 (8) was utilized to conduct land cover and land surface analyses. A composite band analysis was employed to identify the various land cover types. The supervised classification method was utilized to perform the land cover analysis (29). Prior to conducting the land cover analysis, ArcMap 10.8 was used to correct the cloud cover on the image.

The Landsat 7 image for 2000 contained some scan lines on the bands, which were also fixed using the GIS software before performing the supervised classification on that imagery.

2.2.1 Accuracy Assessment

The feasibility of the classified images was evaluated through an accuracy assessment to determine the acceptable level of error in the images. The Kappa coefficient statistics (K) was used to calculate the accuracy assessment of the classified images. The area for all categorical land covers were determined using the software and exported in Excel format for the Kappa calculations. A K value greater than 0.80 indicates a strong agreement of the class assessed, while a K value between 0.40-0.80 indicates good agreement, and a K value less than 0.40 indicates poor agreement (8). The Kappa coefficient (K) was determined as follows:

$$\frac{N \sum_{i=1}^r X_{ff} - \sum_{i=1}^r (X_{l+} \cdot X_{+1})}{N^2 - \sum_{i=1}^r (X_{l+} \cdot X_{+1})} \quad (1)$$

Where;

N is the total number of observations in the matrix

r is the number of rows in the matrix

i is the number of columns in the matrix

X_{ff} refers to the number of observations in row r and column i respectively

X_{+1} is the total for row i

X_{l+} the total for column l .

2.2.2 LST Analysis

The Land Surface Temperature (LST) for DE, DW, and DM was extracted using the Landsat imageries that were also used for land cover analysis, for the years 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020. The specific spectral bands used for LST extraction varied depending on the Landsat image utilized. For Landsat 4-5, spectral band 7 was used for temperature surface calculation, while bands 8 and 11 were used for Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) calculation. The following steps were followed for LST calculation:

Step 1 involves calculating the radiance values, which is necessary for converting pixel values (DN) into physical units.

$$L_{\lambda} = M_L Q_{cal} + A_L \quad (2)$$

Where;

L_{λ} = Radiance

A_L = Top Spectral radiance Watts

M_L = Radiance multiplicative band (No.)

Q_{cal} = Quantized and calibrated standard

Step 2: The level of brightness was considered

$$BT = \frac{K_2}{\ln\left(\frac{K_1}{L_{\lambda}} - 1\right)} - 273.15 \quad (3)$$

BT = Top of the atmosphere brightness temperature

L_{λ} = Top spectral radiance Watts/m² s rad μ m

K_1 = K_1 band specific, constant band (No.)

K_2 = K_2 band specific, constant band (No.)

Step 3 involved calculating the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), which is a measure of live green vegetation in the studied areas.

This was done by subtracting the reflectance values in the near-infrared (NIR) band from the reflectance values in the red band and then dividing the result by their sum.

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED} \quad (4)$$

Where;

RED = DN value from the RED band.

NIR = DN values from near infrared band. The near infrared included band 7 and RED band 8 for Landsat 4-5 and near infrared band 8 and RED band 11 for Landsat 8.

Step 4: Proportional Vegetation (PV) was demanded in the analysis

$$\left[PV = \frac{NDVI-NDVI_{min}}{NDVI_{max}+NDVI_{min}} \right]^2 \quad (5)$$

Where;

PV = Proportional Vegetation.

$NDVI$ = DN values from NDVI image.

$NDVI_{min}$ = minimum value from INDVI image.

$NDVI_{max}$ = maximum value from INDVI image.

Step 5: Land surface Temperature in Degree Celsius:

$$LST = BT + W \left(\frac{BT}{14388(E)} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where;

BT = Top of atmosphere brightness temperature.

W = Wavelength of emitted radiance.

E = Land surface Emissivity.

2.2.3 Change Detection Analysis

The change detection technique was employed to determine the magnitude and direction (increase or decrease) of land cover changes over the Dormaa area from 1990 to 2020. Additionally, annual rates of change for the periods 1990-2000, 2000-2010, and 2010-2020 were calculated to quantify the extent of changes that occurred within the study period. Heat maps were generated for the years 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2020 and compared with the classified land cover images to assess the impact of land use and land cover changes (LULC) on temperature in the study districts.

2.2.4 ERA-5 Temperature Analysis

The first step of the SAT analysis involved conducting normality tests to understand the nature of the datasets, as described by (30). The SAT data was subjected to normality tests using both the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) and Shapiro-Wilk (W) tests.

These tests were used to examine how closely the sample data fit a normal distribution, and were chosen for their suitability and general acceptability in normality testing, as well as their complementary nature (6). The null hypothesis for these tests is that the sample distribution is normal, and test scores are compared to normally distributed scores with the same mean and standard deviation.

The equation used for the Shapiro-Wilk test is provided below:

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n a_i x_{(i)}^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \sigma)^2} \quad (7)$$

The equation above shows that x_i represents the ordered sample value, a is a constant obtained from the means, variances, and covariance of the ordered statistics, n is the number of observations, and σ is the sample mean. In addition to the statistical tests, a graphical analysis was conducted to show the long-term variability of the annual and monthly temperatures. The slope coefficient was examined to determine if the data exhibits a positive or negative trend.

2.2.5 Trend Analysis

The Mann-Kendall (MK) trend test was used to determine the trend (type) in the dataset. This is a widely used monotonic non-parametric test for trend testing in climate data (14). The null hypothesis (H_0) in this test is that there is no trend in the dataset. A positive or negative MK test result signifies an increasing or decreasing trend, respectively, and this was supported by Sen's slope estimator test. The Sen's slope estimator captures the magnitude of the trend and is used to check on average how temperature is changing each year (rate of change). The closer the result is to zero (0), the lesser the trend. The sign (+ or -) of the slope indicates if the temperature is increasing or decreasing, respectively. The MK test is adopted because of its robustness and general acceptability in many climate analyses.

Ground validation method and statistical inferences were also conducted to assess the effect of LULC change on LST. The Z-test was used to compare the means of land cover change and LST, and their correlation was also checked and verified using ANOVA.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Land Cover

3.1.1 Land Used/Land Cover Change

The classified LULC maps, depicting built-up areas and non-built ups (forest) of the respective districts, were utilized to evaluate the LULC land cover changes that occurred between 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2020, as shown in Figure 2. It was observed that the year 2010 had the lowest overall accuracy and kappa coefficient, with values of 94.01% and 0.6, respectively, compared to the other adjacent years. The LULC images indicated a significant increase in built-up areas in the districts between 1990-2020, especially from 2010-2020 (Figure 2). Forest areas in the districts were observed to have experienced the greatest loss. This decline in forest cover could be attributed to the increase in built-up areas due to urbanization and agricultural activities, as a means to meet the emerging needs for accommodation, food supply, and employment opportunities within Dormaa and its environs.

Figure 2: Land Cover Changes that occurred in Dormaa Municipality from 1990-2020.

As stated by (7,8), vegetations are cleared for housing and other social amenities to accommodate the demand of developing cities’ population growth. The increased rate of urbanization (57.38%), as observed in figure 2 and table 4, could be explained as a consequence of the rapid growth in population that also occurred in many urban areas in Ghana during the same period between 2010–2020 (26).

Class names	LULC 1990		LULC 2000		LULC 1990–2000			
	Area (km2)	Cover (%)	Area (km2)	Cover (%)	Area change (km2)	Cover change (%)	Annual rate of change (km2/year)	Annual rate of change (%)
(%/year)								
Waterbody	0.29	0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-
Forest	2107.58	97.64	2043.23	94.66	-64.35	-2.98	-6.43	-0.3
Built-up areas	50.58	2.34	115.2	5.34	64.62	3	6.46	0.3
Total	2158.43	100.00	2158.43	100.00				

Table 2: Land Use Land Cover change analysis from 1990-2000 within the Dormaa Municipality.

Class names	LULC 2000		LULC 2010		LULC 2000-2010			
	Area (km2)	Cover (%)	Area (km2)	Cover (%)	Area change (km2)	Cover change (%)	Annual rate of change	Annual rate of change

							(km2/ year)	
(%/year)								
Forest	2043.23	94.66	1711.77	79	-331.46	-15.66	-33.15	-1.6
Built-up areas	115.2	5.34	446.66	21	331.46	15.66	33.15	1.6
Total	2158.43	100.00	2158.43	100.00				

Table 3: Land Use Land Cover change analysis from 2000-2010 within the Dormaa Municipality.

Class names	LULC 2010		LULC 2020		LULC 2010-2020			
	Area (km2)	Cover (%)	Area (km2)	Cover (%)	Area change (km2)	Cover change (%)	Annual rate of change (km2/year)	Annual rate of change
(%/year)								
Forest	1711.77	79	869.47	40.28	-842.23	-38.72	-84.22	-3.87
Built-up areas	446.66	21	1288.96	59.72	842.23	38.72	84.22	3.87
Total	2158.43	100.00	2158.43	100				

Table 4: Land Use Land Cover change analysis from 2000-2010 within the Dormaa Municipality.

The rapid growth in population in Dormaa Municipal in Ghana is due to mass migration of expatriates from nearby towns on the Ivorian border into the area for business purposes (18,25,26). This has led to an increase in housing stocks and urbanization. The creation of new districts has opened up job opportunities and attracted more migrants seeking greener pastures. The population of the districts has increased drastically since 2000 (18), with associated increases in housing stock and urbanization. Migration has played a significant role in population growth, with the high inter-regional migration being a result of the agriculture and related activities that form the backbone of the districts' economy. However, the high population density has put pressure on social infrastructure such as schools, water, health facilities, and sanitation (8). Vegetation is cleared for housing and other social amenities purposes to accommodate the demand of the growing population, leading to a rise in the rate of deforestation in forest reserves for timber production and agricultural activities. The main construction materials used for dwelling units in the districts are cement block/concretes and mud brick/earth, while metal sheets are the main roofing material (18). Asphalt roads and construction materials contribute to the warming of the surrounding environments (8).

3.1.2 Land Surface Temperature (LST)

The study revealed an increase in the mean LST across all three governmental administrative districts within the Dormaa Municipality from 1990-2020 (Figure 3 and Table 6). The highest increase in mean LST (4.2 °C) was observed within the DE, and the lowest increase (3.8°C) occurred in the DW.

Figure 3: Land Surface Temperature of Dormaa Municipality in 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020.

Administrative district	1990 LST (°C)	2000 LST (°C)	2010 LST (C)	2020 LST (°C)
Dormaa East	19.23	22.75	21.7	23.45
Dormaa West	19.56	23.32	22.0	23.56
Dormaa Municipal	19.56	23.31	21.7	23.36

Table 5: Mean LST for 1990-2020 within the respective Districts in the Dormaa Municipality.

Year	Maximum temperature (°C)	Minimum temperature (°C)	Mean temperature (°C)
1990	26.67	17.02	19.45
2000	42.98	19.10	23.16
2010	28.2	14.8	21.7
2020	39.55	17.27	23.42

Table 6: Maximum, minimum and mean LST for 1990-2020 within the Dormaa Municipality.

3.2 SAT and LST Variability and the LULCC Correlations with Associated Urbanization.

3.2.1 LST and the LULC change correlation with associated urbanization.

Dormaa East and Dormaa Municipal were noted for increased LST, and they have undergone significant land cover changes over the study period due to urbanization (Figures 2 and 3). Most parts of these districts, which were previously covered with vegetation, have been replaced by built-up areas made of asphalt, concrete, bricks, and stones. These built-up areas contribute to the warming of the surrounding environment by absorbing and producing heat.

Furthermore, to better understand the relationship between land cover changes and LST, the mean values of LST for 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020 were correlated with their corresponding percentage annual rate of change in land cover, resulting in a deterministic factor $R= 0.89$ and a significant F-change of 0.014 at a 95% confidence interval. These results support previous studies (8,19,21,28) that have observed an increase in mean LST in places characterized by the rise in built-up surfaces.

3.2.2 Normality Test Results for SAT

In this test, the probability was taken at a 95% confidence level. H_0 was not accepted at P (significance) < 0.05 , but was accepted at $P > 0.05$. These results (Table 7) indicate that the data followed a normal distribution and could be used for trend analysis.

Districts/tests	Shapiro-Wilk		Kolmogorov-Smirnov			
	W	P	K-S	P	Kurtosis	Skewness
DM	0.98	0.82	0.08	0.200	-0.346	0.114
DW	0.97	0.53	0.11	0.200	-0.357	0.084
DE	0.98	0.85	0.09	0.200	-0.506	-0.086

Table 7: Normality test of annual temperature. Significance at 0.05, Reject H_0 at < 0.05 level or accept H_1 at > 0.05 .

3.2.3 Trends and Variability in Mean Annual SAT

As shown (Figure 4), annual mean temperatures at the districts showed a strong statistically significant positive trend. A linear regression trend line was used to show evidence of the temperature variability and trend in the dataset.

Figure 4: Inter-decadal temperature increases were observed in the different districts. The blue, orange, and green colours represent the temperature increases in DM, DE, and DW respectively, while the broken black line indicates the rising temperature trend. It was observed that in all three districts, the SAT had increased significantly over the 30-year study period which was supported by Sen's slope.

3.3 The Impacts of Rising Temperatures in Dormaa and the Necessity for Further Analysis to Guide Conservation Efforts.

3.3.1 Effects of Increasing Temperatures in the Dormaa Area.

The increasing temperature in the area has significant consequences for the residents' livelihoods (18). The significant rise in temperature implies that it has the potential to disturb rainfall figures through evapotranspiration (20,22,24), leading to a scarcity of water in the area, as observed in the drying-up of rivers and soil moisture deficiency. This is a major setback to farming in the area, as farmers depend on rain-fed agriculture (26). However, it cannot be denied that the rising LST and SAT in the area are partly attributed to anthropogenic activities such as deforestation for charcoal production and timber, clearing of vegetation for farming, population pressure on the environment, urbanization, sand mining, and urban heating.

Furthermore, the continuous rise in LST and SAT would lead to the incessant occurrence of respiratory diseases in many overcrowded areas in the city. Warming promotes agricultural pests and (31) diseases, thereby increasing risks for crop yields (32). Additionally, a greater frequency of extreme events such as droughts, floods, and heatwaves would inevitably damage crop production.

Residents would still be uncertain about temperature variations in the subsequent years. Therefore, a comprehensive evaluation of expected mean and extreme climate events under climate change and their related consequences should be an essential component of efforts to promote agricultural development and reduce high temperature-related infections in the Dormaa districts.

The need for Further Analysis of the Study's Findings to inform Conservation Efforts in the Dormaa Area.

3.3.2 The Need for Further Analysis of the Study's Findings to Inform Conservation Efforts in the Dormaa Area.

The study's findings suggest that Land Use Land Cover Change (LULCC), Land Surface Temperature (LST), and Surface Air Temperature (SAT) are interconnected in the Dormaa area. The analysis revealed a deterministic factor $R=0.89$, with a significant F-change of 0.014 at a 95% confidence interval, indicating that the increase in LST and SAT is linked to significant changes in land cover from 1990-2020. The most significant land cover changes were observed in the Dormaa Municipal, which recorded the highest LST and SAT anomaly change of 0.091°C compared to other districts. The study attributed this to rapid urbanization, which caused a greater portion of the green vegetated surface to be converted to a more non-transpiring and reduced evaporative built-up environment. The relationship between land cover changes and LST is non-linear, highlighting the importance of considering the specific context when analysing this relationship.

Further analysis of the findings could inform conservation efforts in the Dormaa area. The decline in forest cover highlights the need for proactive measures to protect the remaining forested areas and encourage reforestation efforts. Conservation efforts should focus on promoting sustainable land use practices, such as green infrastructure and sustainable agriculture techniques, to minimize the impact of urbanization and agricultural expansion on the environment. Reforestation efforts could also help to restore forest cover and improve the local climate, while also providing important ecosystem services.

Moreover, the study's findings could have important implications for conservation efforts in the region. For example, efforts to reduce urban sprawl and promote sustainable agricultural practices could help to mitigate the negative impacts of land cover changes on temperature. Additionally, conservation strategies that focus on preserving forest cover could help to mitigate the effects of temperature changes on biodiversity and ecosystem services.

Further analysis of the findings could help to identify specific conservation strategies that would be most effective in mitigating the negative impacts of land cover changes on temperature and other ecological processes. By delving deeper into the implications of the findings for conservation efforts, the study could inform more effective conservation strategies tailored to the specific needs of the Dormaa area. Overall, the study highlights the need for a holistic approach to land use planning and management that takes into account the complex interrelationships between human activities, land cover changes, and climate.

4.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

The study has established an upward trend in SAT and LST over the study period in the three districts. Nearly all districts have warmed at a similar rate of 0.031°C over the past three decades, with minimal changes occurring in their annual anomalies ($0.091^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$, $0.091^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$, and $0.089^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ for DM, DW, and DE, respectively). The study found a significant increase in mean SAT during the period 1990-2020 in all the Dormaa districts. Remote sensing data and GIS techniques were used to assess the impact of land cover changes on LST in the Dormaa districts from 1990-2020. The conversion of green vegetated surfaces to non-transpiring and reduced evaporative built-up in the Dormaa Municipal due to population growth resulted in clearing vegetation for housing, social amenities, and commercial centres to meet the needs of the ever-increasing population since 1990. The rise in economic activities with population growth contributed to the overall increase in LST over all districts, as observed from the 1990-2020 Landsat heat maps. Therefore, it is evident that both LST and SAT are rising, fluctuating, and varying with time in the study area, which could lead to the occurrence of diseases and infections, damage crop production, and subsequently reduce agricultural yield in the area. Therefore, a comprehensive evaluation of expected mean and extreme climate events under climate change and the related consequences should be an essential component of efforts to promote agricultural development in the Dormaa districts. Thus, all stakeholders, including non-governmental organizations and the government, are recommended to ensure and help protect vegetation, which serves as a carbon sink, by enforcing laws and regulations in the districts,

particularly in the Dormaa Municipal. The study also suggested the need for proper mitigation and adaptive policies in town planning to minimize the effects of heat stress in the area, as most urban cities in Africa continue to grow at a rate of 4.87% per annum. The inhabitants in the area should also integrate innovative urban sustainability practices (green walls, green roofs, green spaces, white or reflective materials) in the construction of buildings, roofs, pavements, and roads to help increase albedo and aid in reflecting about 50% light, thus reducing or regulating LST and SAT in the Dormaa Municipal. Moreover, to mitigate the increase in LST and SAT, habitats in the Dormaa area should adhere to the use of other renewable energy sources (solar or biofuel technologies). This will help limit the impacts of biomass burning and combustion of fossil fuels for energy production and reduce their harmful effects. Overall, the study's findings highlight the need for proactive measures to mitigate the adverse effects of increasing temperatures in the Dormaa districts.

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